

DIGITAL LITERACY AMONG SCIENCE TEACHERS: A LOOK POST PANDEMIC

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Digital Literacy among Science Teachers: A Look Post Pandemic

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Abstract

Digital literacy is vital in the 21st century teaching and learning in order to create a meaningful educative process for both teachers and students. Also, it is a necessity to adapt in this fast-changing digital age. This study seeks to determine the level of digital literacy skills that teachers need, as well as the level of digital literacy skills among science teachers in public secondary schools and how these abilities relate to gender, age, experience as a teacher, and educational attainment. This study utilized quantitative descriptive survey design which addressed the purpose of this study. The target respondents were the 50 public high school science teachers in select schools in Iligan City, Lanao del Norte and Misamis Oriental. Complete enumeration was the sampling technique used. An ACDC (Analysis of Common Digital Competences) questionnaire was utilized abilities to measure how respondents perceived their own digital competencies. It was adapted from Sanchez-Cruzado, et., al (2021) and was based on the European Commission's (EC) DigiComp framework for citizens' digital competencies. It comprised of five (5) digital skills: Information and information literacy, Communication and collaboration, Creation of digital Content, Security and Problem resolution. The inventory questionnaire consists of 47 Likert-scale items (4 = very high, 3 = high, 2 = low, 1 = very low) consisting of 8 items for Information and information literacy, 7 items for Communication and collaboration, 14 items for Creation of digital Content, 6 items for Security and 12 items for Problem resolution. To test the reliability, Cronbach alpha was administered with the result of 0.94. The results show that the overall Digital literacy level of science teachers in select schools in Iligan city division is "Fair". Moreover, only age and years of teaching experience are the variables that have a negative correlation to the level of Digital literacy.

Keywords: *digital literacy, education, in-service science high school teachers, information and information literacy*

Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic has certainly caused the worst disruption in education in human history, aside from fatalities and economic disruptions. Governments all around the world employed social isolation, lockdowns, and temporary school closures to stop the disease's transmission, which had a significant impact on daily routines and activities (Lee, 2020). According to information from UNESCO 2020, an unprecedented scenario has arisen as a result of the confinement of more than 1500 million students and their instructors worldwide starting in 2019.

Unexpectedly, it has had a significant impact on education around the world, forcing a switch to online teaching and learning for both educators and students. All participants faced a significant difficulty as educators and students had to progressively adjust to the new educational environment. Undoubtedly, full online education during the COVID-19 pandemic or flexible learning modalities resulted in changes to professional roles, job fulfillment, and digital literacy needs for teachers. Teachers must possess adequate digital literacy to teach students online within the present educational model. Still, the educative process could not be full and complete just by digital literacy alone. (Sánchez-Cruzado et., al, 2021).

Consequently, it has evaluated many other facets of the educational system, including teachers' digital literacy (Trivino-Cabrera et al., 2021). Many studies have focused on the stress experienced by teachers during the first few months of forced confinement (Al-Marouf et al., 2020; Devitt et al., 2020), which still has an impact on them (Cervený, 2021). Because of the apparent absence of technology in schools, as well as in the homes of teachers and students, this stress on teachers has been substantially generated (Ramsetty & Adams, 2020). Teachers are vital members of the institutions that support teaching and learning in the context of education. The responsibility for the growth of students has been placed in their hands. Furthermore, it is essential that teachers improve their digital literacy. Teachers must acquire new and improved skills in order to work with and incorporate technology into their lessons. Making students feel at ease and included in this digital age is crucial. A computer-proficient teacher can provide more in-depth training by making use of the numerous programs and resources available to them. With the different students in mind, the teacher can design lesson plans and delivery strategies that are most effective for each unique student. Digitally proficient teachers can even impart their knowledge to their colleagues, raising teaching standards.

Digital literacy is a notion that is part of 21st century skills, and its application increases every day. This ability has strengthened interpersonal communication as a result of the diversity of digital technologies, the ease of information sharing, and the widespread usage of content production (Kazakoff, 2014; Dowdall, 2009; Menzietin and Akkoyunlu, 2017). Digital literacy is the ability to assess the reliability and quality of information found in a digital environment, as well as the complex cognitive, sociological, and emotional skills needed by users to create new, meaningful materials on graphical screens and read the instructions that appear on them. Gliner (1997) originally defined digital literacy as the skill to understand and use the information accessed on various digital sources. Opportunities for quick and direct communication arose as a result of the transformation process, which diversified the ways that information was sent. Another definition is that it is the capacity to use information technology and the internet to discover, assess,

consume, exchange, and create content (Pilgrim & Martinez, 2013). It is the capacity to communicate on digital platforms, such as computers and mobile devices, and is defined by the American Library Association task force as "the ability to use information and communication technologies to find, evaluate, create, and communicate information." Digital literacy, on the other hand, expands on traditional notions of literacy by addressing competencies relating to computers and other digital devices, the internet, and social media. The capacity to comprehend and use data from a wide range of sources in a number of formats is known as digital literacy. In this sense, it's important to be able to both discover and utilize things (Jones & Flannigan, 2006 in Erol and Ayadin, 2021).

According to the National Institute of Educational Technologies and Teacher Training (INTEF), an organization under the Ministry of Education, Culture, and Sports of Spain, the Common Framework for Teaching Digital Competence (DigComp) is a reference framework for the assessment and development of teachers' digital skills. These abilities are referred to as skills that teachers in the 21st century require in order improve instructional strategies and continue their professional development.

The DigComp framework specifies the five categories that make up teachers' digital competence:

Information and information literacy: The ability to recognize, track down, obtain, store, arrange, and evaluate digital information while determining its applicability and purpose to educational requirements.

Communication and collaboration: the ability to engage and take part in communities and networks; to communicate in digital settings; to exchange resources using online technologies; to connect with and cooperate with others; and to be interculturally aware.

Creation of Digital Content: the ability to produce artistic works, multimedia material, computer programming, and the expertise to use intellectual property rights and licenses. the ability to integrate and rebuild past knowledge and content.

Security: For the safeguarding of private data and information, safeguarding of digital identities, safeguarding of digital content, safeguarding of security measures, and for the prudent and secure use of technology.

Problem resolution: the ability to recognize needs in the use of digital resources and resolve problems encountered. This is done through: selecting the most appropriate digital tool, according to the task at hand, address conceptual problems with digital tools or media, use technology in a creative way, resolve technical issues, and improve one's own and others' competence.

According to the European Commission (2003), digital literacy without it, individuals cannot fully engage in society or get the skills and knowledge required to survive in the twenty- first century. Digital literacy is quickly becoming a necessity for creativity, innovation, and entrepreneurship. Technology has been observed to have a significant influence on nearly all facets of education, allowing students to study more quickly and easily whenever and wherever they choose. As a result, it encourages students to take an active part in their learning. Numerous studies have shown that age, experience, and gender of teachers are among the factors that influence how well ICT is integrated into teaching and learning. But in education, both teachers and technology play significant roles. It is emphasized that effective teachers and cutting-edge technology are necessary to improve education. Teachers' levels of high or poor digital competence in upper secondary school are somewhat predicted by demographic, personal, and professional factors such age, job experience, gender, educational achievement, and ICT training. According to several studies (Gokdas and Cam, 2022; Sanchez-Cruzado, et., al, 2021; Umugiraneza et al., 2018; Vidal, et., al, 2022; Fernandez-Cruz, et., al, 2016; Oçal, 2017; Arslan, 2019; Gomez-Trigueros and Ortega- Sanchez, 2019; and Korkmaz, 2020), digital literacy abilities may have a significant impact on teachers' learning and professional growth processes.

Correspondingly, the science curriculum acknowledges the role that technology and science contribute in day-to-day human activities. Science and technology are intertwined in social, economic, personal, and ethical domains of existence. In order to preserve our country's cultural legacy, the scientific curriculum promotes a tight interaction between science and technology, especially indigenous technology. Inquiry-based and learner-centered, the scientific curriculum for grades K–12 emphasizes the use of information to build explanations. Concepts and skills in the life sciences, physics, chemistry, and earth sciences are taught at increasingly complex levels from one grade level to the next in a spiral progression, enabling a greater understanding of important ideas. A meaningful comprehension of concepts and their application to real-life circumstances will result from the integration of science issues with other disciplines (DepEd Science Curriculum, 2016).

In the Philippines, more than 80% of public schools across all basic education levels had working computers as of SY 2020–2021, which are utilized for both instructional and administrative purposes. The proportion of computer units to students throughout all basic education levels is as follows: 1:19 for elementary school, 1:9 for junior high school, and 1:3 for senior high school. As for public schools, 64.2% of elementary schools, 72.2% of junior high schools, and 67.3% of senior high schools have internet connection (DepEd Data Bits, 2022 in Espinosa, et. al, 2023). Just 1.8% of the 47 in the nation. Free public WiFi is available at 421 public schools (Philippine News Agency, 2022). Additionally, the Open Educational Resources (OER) have been defined by the Department of Education (DepEd) as an innovative method to connect the disconnected schools. It focuses on ICT-assisted teaching and learning, with localized resources that can be adjusted to provide everyone, even those in schools with inadequate internet access, with high-quality, useful, and suitable education. Because Open Educational Resources (OER) are designed to teach 21st century skills, robust interactivity, and modernization, they help learners become ready for a changing world. Adopting open educational resources (OER) can help the public school system overcome its obstacles, particularly for "last mile" schools—those located in remote locations with

limited access to learning resources and little capacity to produce and reuse information (Peregrino, et. al, 2020). The Department of Education (DepEd) has launched a number of initiatives to support educators and learners in enhancing their ICT and digital literacy. These include the following: (1) DepEd Commons, a library of free online learning resources for educators and students; (2) Digital Rise Program, an extensive digital literacy training program for educators, parents, and students; and (3) Learning Management System (LMS), an online learning platform. The policies outlined in DepEd Order No. 12, Series of 2021, "Implementing Guidelines on the Use of ICT in the K-12 Education Program," specify how teachers are to integrate ICT into the K-12 curriculum.

Unfortunately, despite of these, studies in the Philippines reveal that there is a lack of knowledge and confidence in the full utilization of technology among teachers in the Philippines. Additionally, a digital divide exists and affects Filipino students in terms of inadequate access to digital devices and internet connectivity in both homes and schools (DKAP Philippine Report, 2020). For Filipino learners to acquire their digital skills, their teachers must possess the necessary digital skills and tools. Nonetheless, there are disparities in digital literacy among educators as well, particularly with regard to digital abilities (Nueva, 2019). Although school principals claim that PISA 2018 findings show that Filipino teachers possess the technical and pedagogical abilities, as well as the support and resources needed for digital learning, Filipino teachers may have diverse opinions regarding their preparedness for remote learning (World Bank, 2020). Another study by Fabito, Trillanes, and Sarmiento (2020) indicates that during the pandemic, neither faculty members nor students were adequately prepared for online learning, and they provide a framework for developing meaningful learning experiences for students. This is concurrent with research by De Vera et al. (2021), which discovered that Filipino teachers struggle to integrate educational technology into lesson plans. Developing assessment methods and processes with digital content and platforms, creating educational materials with online applications, and adjusting to new software and technology were some of these problems. Teachers found it difficult to incorporate ICT resources into their lessons since there were few professional development opportunities pertaining to technology integration and little assistance for ICT resources. According to David and Aruta (2022), it is critical to assist Filipino teachers in understanding and appreciating the convenience and utility that technology may offer to both students and teachers in order to enhance their intents to use it. This can be achieved by giving teachers enough training on how to use technology to build students' digital abilities at different grade levels, as well as by equipping them with appropriate technological equipment.

Moreover, there have been less publications written about this digital readiness and capacity issue of teachers in the Philippine. It is assumed that fewer literature related to this research study has been made available in secondary high schools. Most of the time, students' usage of technology is the main focus rather than the teachers such as the studies of Balmeo et al. (2014), Garzon, Kim, and Kim, (2019), and Javier and Dirain (2019), all emphasized how student academic performance is impacted by the use of technology in teaching and learning.

Thus, because of these pressing needs, this study therefore seeks to determine the level of digital literacy skills that teachers need as well as the level of digital literacy skills among science teachers in public secondary schools and its association to gender, age, teaching experience and educational attainment; determine ways through which teachers can apply digital literacy skills in the solution to classroom instructional problems; and determine what importance digital literacy skills hold for the classroom teacher. This study will help contribute in assessing, preparing and equipping teacher's digital literacy in responding to the new trends in teaching and learning as well as adding literatures on digital literacy on teachers in the Philippines.

Research Questions

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of Digital Literacy among in-service Science teachers in terms of the following digital skills as measured by the digital literacy questionnaire/ ACDC (Analysis of Common Digital Competences) questionnaire?
 - 1.1. information and information literacy
 - 1.2. communication and collaboration
 - 1.3. creation of digital content
 - 1.4. security
 - 1.5. problem resolution
2. How do the in-service Science teachers' level of digital literacy differ when grouped according to:
 - 2.1. gender
 - 2.2. age
 - 2.3. years of teaching
 - 2.4. educational Attainment
3. Is there a significant relationship between the independent variables and Digital literacy?

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized quantitative descriptive survey which addressed the purpose of this study. The survey research is designed to describe characteristics of a population or group (Fraenkel et al., 2012). It is essentially a quantitative research technique in which a

sample of people, or sometimes the entire population, is given a survey or questionnaire to describe their attitudes, opinions, behaviors, experiences, or other characteristics of the population (Creswell, 2005).

Respondents

The target respondents were the 50 public high school science teachers in select schools in Iligan City, Lanao del Norte and Misamis Oriental. Complete enumeration was the sampling technique used.

Instruments

The researcher utilized the ACDC (Analysis of Common Digital Competences) questionnaire adapted from Sanchez-Cruzado, et., al (2021) has been employed as an instrument because it is thought to be suited to obtaining the purpose of eliciting digital literacy. The questionnaire was based on the European Commission's (EC) DigiComp framework for citizens' digital abilities to measure how respondents perceived their own digital competencies. This model was also applied in the UNESCO-conducted study by Law, Woo, De la Torre, and Wong (2018) to suggest a global framework of reference for digital literacy. It comprised of five (5) digital skills: Information and information literacy, Communication and collaboration, Creation of digital Content, Security and Problem resolution of in-service teachers. The inventory questionnaire consists of 47 Likert-scale items (4 = very high, 3 = high, 2 = low, 1 = very low) consisting of 8 items for Information and information literacy, 7 items for Communication and collaboration, 14 items for Creation of digital Content, 6 items for Security and 12 items for Problem resolution. To test the reliability, Cronbach alpha was administered with the result of 0.94.

Data Analysis

The study was undertaken only after obtaining permission and informed consent from relevant authorities.. The data were acquired from the 50 in-service public high school Science teachers as the respondents thru the Digital literacy questionnaire. To describe the in-service teachers' level of digital literacy, descriptive statistical tools including the original data's mean and standard deviation were employed. The researcher carried out independent T-test, ANOVA and Pearson Correlation to compare and determine if the variables differ statistically significant from one another.

Table 1. *Scoring guide*

<i>Digital Literacy</i>	<i>Scale</i>
Excellent	4.10-5.00
Good	3.10-4.00
Fair	2.10-3.00
Poor	1.00-2.00

Ethical Considerations

An informed consent was provided to individuals, and participation in the study was entirely voluntary. The study's goals and objectives were communicated clearly with the participants. The study was not predicted to affect any physical or psychological harm. At any point throughout the research, participants can opt out. The use of offensive, discriminatory, or other objectionable words in the questionnaire were strictly prohibited. The respondents' privacy and identities were protected by a research-created code for each respondent. Only the researcher has access to the data, which will be deleted after one year. In any publication, only processed and summarized data were published, and where direct quote was required, the respondents were given a codename. Any form, report, or write-up that contained identifiable information were redacted. Prior to data collection, all required permissions were requested.

Results and Discussion

Table 2. *Digital Literacy level of in-service Science teachers*

<i>Digital Skills</i>	<i>Knowledge</i>			<i>Usage</i>		
	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
Information and information literacy	3.4	0.59	Good	3.4	0.63	Good
Communication and collaboration	3.2	0.60	Good	3.1	0.65	Good
Creation of digital Content	3.0	0.69	Fair	3.0	0.65	Fair
Security	3.0	0.65	Fair	2.9	0.61	Fair
Problem resolution	2.9	0.72	Fair	2.8	0.78	Fair
Total	3.1	0.18	Good	3.0	0.21	Fair
Overall	3.0					Fair

Table 2 above shows the overall Digital literacy level of 3.0 which has a descriptive rating of "Fair". In terms of "knowledge" and "usage" according to each digital skill, the Information and information literacy skill and Communication and Collaboration both have "Good" with a mean of 3.4 and 3.2 respectively under "Knowledge" while under "Usage" both have 3.4 and 3.1 means respectively. The other Digital skills such as Creation of digital Content, Security and Problem resolution have all "Fair" ratings on both

“Knowledge” and “Usage” with 3.0, 3.0, 2.9 (Knowledge) means respectively and 3.0, 2.9, 2.8 (Usage) means respectively.

The same digital literacy questionnaire was used in a study of Sitoy et al. (2021) of 287 public and private school teachers in Cebu, Philippines, and the findings revealed that the respondents' profiles scored highly for information processing, communication, and safety. Information processing, which includes data management and organization, is the capacity to recognize the information that is required, to know how to effectively search for and recover data, and to confirm the information's source and substance (Law, Woo, De la Torre, & Wong, 2018).

Teachers use the internet for a variety of purposes. Some of these include research, finding low-cost or free teaching resources, attending seminars for professional development, connecting their classrooms to the rest of the world, and many more. The capacity to cooperate, engage, communicate, and exchange information through digital technology is another aspect of the communication indicator. When in-person meetings or physical presence are not an option, teachers can still meet with students and continue lessons utilizing a variety of media.

The findings above indicate that the digital literacy or competences need to be updated. Two of the most crucial elements in raising students' accomplishment levels are high-quality instruction and strong school leadership. One of an institution's best practices is to invest in professional development for teachers in order to enhance their knowledge and abilities (Fauth, et al., 2019; Wahyuddin, 2017; Mizell, 2010). Students would benefit from a more engaging learning environment and experience if their teachers were more qualified and experienced. Then, new teaching strategies that will meet or address the students' learning needs or challenges are presented to them.

More technologically savvy than their previous generations, today's students use the internet and other digital tools for the majority of their everyday tasks. As the focus shifts to student learning, teaching using technology provides educators with a multitude of opportunities to enhance student outcomes (Sitoy et al., 2021). Therefore, teachers that are adept at using technology in the classroom benefit from it. Students' dependence on smart gadgets and technology makes it easy for them to adapt to technologically sophisticated learning environments, such as blended learning, flipped classrooms, and online programs. The global spread of the COVID-19 virus has forced educators to reach out to students who are unable to attend class in person through the use of technology (Anft, 2020). For teachers who are accustomed to and proficient with technology it would be easy and comfortable, but it may be difficult for those who are not. Then, it is imperative and desirable that pre-service teachers be trained digital literacy or that professional development in this field be given top priority, for educators to effectively utilize diverse digital technologies to meet the needs of their students.

Table 3. *Digital Literacy versus Gender*

<i>Gender</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>F-value</i>	<i>P-value</i>
Male	3.1	Good	0.296	0.600

When grouped according to gender, the Digital literacy among in-service teachers is not statistically significant as shown in table 3 above with $F(1,8.72) = 0.296$ and $p = ns$. This indicates that Digital literacy level whether male or female do not differ statistically. Thus, the null hypothesis is to be accepted. In a research published in 2019, Guillén-Gámez et al. investigated the sex differences in blog usage among 134 potential English-speaking primary school teachers.

Males scored somewhat higher than females, but there were no noticeable difference, according to the results. Other related studies, like the one conducted by Cakir (2013), stating that men are often seen as having greater competence (Lucas et al., 2021). Similar with the findings of Korkmaz (2020), male classroom teachers had greater levels of digital literacy than female classroom teachers did.

However, other studies (Tondeur et al., 2018; Fernandez-Batanero et al., 2019) have not discovered any differences in the specific uses of digital technology based on sex. According to the findings that supported the findings of this study (Argelagos and Pifarre, 2017; Arslan, 2019; Karagözü and Gezer, 2022; Kozan and Bulut zek, 2019; Ocağ and Karakuş, 2019; Tomczyk, 2020; and Van Deursen and Van Diepen, 2013), there was no statistically significant difference between the levels of digital literacy of male and female science teachers.

One may argue that males use technology more effectively than women and that they are more curious about and interested in technical advancements in general. On the other hand, women's attitudes and perceptions of utilizing technology may have improved as a result of the expanded projects and educational initiatives focused at improving the digital citizenship abilities of female students (Gokdaş and Cam, 2022). This is because women have increasingly participated effectively in the digitalization process. This may be the reason why there is no statistical significant gender difference in digital literacy.

Table 4. *Digital Literacy versus Age*

<i>Age</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>F-value</i>	<i>P-value</i>
Millennials (27 to 42)	3.18	Good	6.52	0.01*
Gen X (43 to 58)	2.76	Fair		

Table 4 above shows that there is a significant statistical difference of Digital literacy according to Age/generation with $F(1,48) = 6.52$ and $p \leq 0.01$. The null hypothesis is to be rejected. The findings shows that those who are younger, specifically ages 27 to 42

(Millennials) years old have significantly higher digital literacy levels than those who are older, ages 43 to 58 years old (Gen X).

Similar findings were obtained in other studies by Korkmaz (2020) and Erol and Aydin (2021), which revealed that classroom instructors' levels of digital literacy fell as they became older. Erolu (2019) claims that as educators get older and more experienced, the utilization of technology also declines. On the other hand, Cin (2018) found that in a different study, teachers with less experience use technology more frequently. This phenomenon can be explained by the fact that new teachers are more likely to be exposed to technology early in their careers, use it more frequently, and learn about its integration into the classroom during their undergraduate studies. Furthermore, Yeşildal (2018) observed a similar relationship between age and digital literacy, showing that as people aged, their level of digital literacy declined. This scenario may be explained by the fact that younger people utilize digital media more frequently and are more familiar with the fast evolving and spreading opportunities for technology than older people.

It is critical to study how teachers from the generations known as Baby Boomers and Generation X—those who were born in the 1940s and 1960s—adapt to the digital world since it is well known that instructors from these groups lag behind in the adoption of new technologies because of their advanced age. It has been observed that teachers from Generation X and Baby Boomer backgrounds struggle to use information technology effectively. It is clear from the study's general conclusions that Gen X and Baby Boomer educators are attempting to adapt to the needs of the digital era. However, there are times when they feel as though they are lacking in particular areas (Gunduzalp, 2021). Kocaolu (2015) conducted study on the use of interactive smart boards by teachers and found that teachers with more years of experience are less proficient than teachers of younger age groups.

Table 5. *Digital Literacy versus Teaching experience*

<i>Years of Teaching</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>F-value</i>	<i>P-value</i>
21-30 years	2.8	Fair	2.98	0.04*
11-20 years	2.7	Fair		
6-10 years	3.2	Good		
0-5 years	3.3	Good		

As shown in table 5 above, the Digital Literacy is statistically significant when grouped according to teaching experience with $F(2,46)=2.98$ and p value of 0.04. Thus, the null hypothesis is to be rejected. Dunn's test was used as a post hoc test. It reveals that those who are teaching in their early years, 10 years and less of teaching experience ($M=3.3$ and 3.2 , $s=0.95$) have higher Digital literacy levels compared to those who are teaching for more than 11 years ($M=2.7$ and 2.8 , $s=0.95$), $p < .05$. These findings suggests that the years of teaching affects the digital literacy level. This is in congruence to other findings that there is a negative correlation between years of teaching and digital literacy (Lucas et al., 2021; Öçal, 2017); Arslan, 2019); Gomez- Trigueros, Ruiz- Banuls and Ortega- Sanchez, 2019; Korkmaz, 2020). According to Gokdaş and Cam's study from 2022, among the 88 science teachers in Turkey, those with less professional experience are better at using digital technology than those with more expertise. However, studies show that the likelihood of having higher digital competence increases with years of teaching experience (Benali et al., 2018; Guillén-Gámez et al., 2020). Fernández-Batanero et al. (2019) conducted a more in- depth analysis of 777 in-service teachers' levels of digital competence with regard to using ICT resources to support students with disabilities and discovered a significant correlation between the level of digital competence and the number of years of teaching experience. In contrast, Tomczyk (2020) and Yontar (2019) found no evidence of a substantial difference in secondary school teachers' levels of digital literacy according to the length of their teaching experience. The similar ages of the two groups and the lack of sufficient study participants were given as explanations for why there was no difference in pre-service teachers' digital literacy between those aged 22 and under and those aged 21 and under.

Levels of digital literacy decrease as years of work experience increase. This may be the result of new teachers incorporating the usage of digital technology into every aspect of their lives in order to meet the demands of the digital age. Additionally, new teachers may have completed more courses in digital technology use during their studies in school than teachers with an extensive amount of professional experience. The older teachers may have entered the world of the internet and digital technologies relatively late in life, which makes it challenging for them to adjust to the digital world which may also be the cause of this problem (Gokdas and Cam, 2022).

Table 6. *Digital Literacy versus Educational Attainment*

<i>Highest Educational Attainment</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>F-value</i>	<i>P-value</i>
Full-pledge Doctorate	2.9	Fair	1.07	0.383
Doctoral units	2.9	Fair		
Full-pledge Masters	3.3	Good		
Masteral units	2.8	Fair		
Undergraduate	3.0	Fair		

In terms of highest educational attainment, it is statistically not significant with $F(4,45)=1.07$, $p=ns$ as shown in table 6 above. Thus, the null hypothesis should be accepted. This is corroborated by the studies of Vidal, et., al, (2022) and Fernández-Cruz, et., al, (2016) that, there is no significant relationship with their degree of digital literacy skills and educational attainment. However, several studies suggest that teachers with advanced degrees would possess more digital proficiency (Sánchez-Cruzado, at al., 2021; Umugiraneza et

al., 2018). This is because continuous professional development is positively associated with proficiency (Sanchez, et al., 2020).

Table 7. Gender, Age, Teaching experience and Educational attainment associate with their Digital Literacy

	Gender		Age		Teaching experience		Highest Educational Attainment	
	Pearson r	p-value	Pearson r	p-value	Pearson r	p-value	Pearson r	p-value
Digital Literacy Mean= 3.0	-.071	.622	-.346	*.014	-.329	*.020	.043	.765
		NS						NS
	1.9		2.4		2.5		2.1	

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05

With a Pearson r value of $-.346$ and a p-value of 0.014 for Age and Pearson r value of $-.329$ and a p-value of $.020$ for teaching experience, there is a strong negative and significant association between Age and Digital Literacy as well as Teaching experience and Digital Literacy (given in table 7). As a result, the null hypothesis must be rejected. The findings of this study suggests that the lower the age and teaching experience of science teachers, the higher the Digital literacy level.

Results of other studies indicate otherwise on this study's findings. Fernández-Batanero et al. (2019), in Guillén-Gámez et al. (2022), conducted an extensive investigation to assess the level of digital competency among 777 in-service teachers in relation to utilizing ICT tools to assist students with disabilities. It was discovered that the amount of years spent educating was shown to be significant and positively correlated with the level of digital competency. Furthermore, it was found by Nwankwor (2021) and Dias-Trindade et al. (2020) that an individual's age has no influence on their degree of digital competency.

A number of studies, however, have supported up these conclusions, showing a negative relationship between age and digital literacy (Oçal, 2017; Arslan, 2019; Gomez- Trigueros, Ruiz- Banuls, and Ortega- Sanchez, 2019; Korkmaz, 2020; Basantes et al., 2020; and Gokdas and Cam, 2022). Additionally, Guillén-Gámez et al. (2021) discovered that a teacher's age affects their level of digital competence. In their study, educators with less than 10 years of experience and those under the age of 40 had a greater degree of competency. Similar findings were made by Napal Fraile et al. (2018), who created a self-assessment tool based on DigComp and discovered a negative relationship between age and digital competence, especially in the field of content creation. Furthermore, Guillén-Gámez and Mayorga-Fernández (2019) discovered differences in terms of years of experience and age, and they suggested that these factors hindered the development of digital competence. In the same context, Benali et al. (2018) found that teachers with more years of experience have greater levels of digital competence.

This might be because older teachers were introduced to the internet and digital technology relatively late in life, which makes it challenging for them to adjust to the digital environment (Gokdas and Cam, 2022). Most people who work as teachers are young, both in age and profession. Because of this, younger teachers with less professional experience are more familiar with new technologies than more experienced teachers, and they find it easier to adapt to shifts in the process that people learn. Oftentimes, older educators are restless and resistant to learning anything new— in this case, learning using digital technologies. Furthermore, older educators sometimes overlook information that could discourage them from mastering digital technologies. However, younger educators have superior recall and are more positive and enthusiastic about anything new (Rahimi and Yodollahi, 2011; Yates, et., al., 2015; Singh, et., al, 2018; Ramadan, et., al, 2018; and Saripudin, et., al, 2021).

Conclusions

The Digital literacy of the 50 in-service Science teachers of the select schools of the Division of Iligan city is “Fair” with age and years of teaching experience are the only variables that have a negative correlation to the level of Digital literacy. The younger the age, the higher the level of Digital literacy among science teachers. This points out that, there is a need for upgrading the competencies and capacities of our teachers in the field particularly those who are in the older generations. Specifically, on Creation of digital Content, Security and Problem resolution where majority of respondents have “Fair” ratings in which are all vital in surviving in this digital age.

With the 21st century teaching-learning and the present K-12 curriculum that we are in today and the new laws on cybercrime and data privacy, it is but timely and appropriate to respond to this urging immediate need for Digital literacy not only for students but more so for teachers. Teachers are tasked with the responsibility of facilitating learning and continuously guiding each student on a variety of useful strategies as per the department's mandate (Tuazon, 2019). Since effective teachers affect student learning (Fauth et al., 2019; Akram, 2019), it is important to have competent teachers. Additionally, the organization's success depends on how proficient the teachers are to use these technologies in the classroom. This is mostly because using online learning requires specific competencies and abilities from the user (Javier, 2020; Ventayen, 2019). As the front-runners in education, teachers are playing a more important role in educational settings, especially in virtual teaching and learning environments, as the COVID-19 pandemic proved. This has sped up the process of virtualizing education. The digitally literate teacher bears the responsibility of educating the students on the reliability and validity of sources, their frequency of updating, and the existence of any more useful websites related to the subject matter. More importantly, it is their obligation to educate the students on whether the material is given in biased or objective language. Teachers have a vital job to do in preparing students for the demands of the digital age, similar to in these next generation learning settings (Ghosh, 2022; Gokbulut, 2019).

Considering the relevance of science to students' everyday lives and the universal problem-solving and critical thinking skills it develops in them, Science education is one of the most important subjects taught in the classroom. Students can come up with ideas, assess options rationally, and even comprehend the research behind public policy decisions thanks to these lifetime abilities. Scientific education provides students with the knowledge and skills they need to succeed in school and beyond when it comes to technology literacy, critical thinking, and problem-solving (Arrieta et al., 2020). According to research (Nawzad, & Said, 2018), in teaching science, utilizing technology need to be mandated since it increases student participation in the educational process, improves achievement levels, and makes it simpler for students to complete their assignments (Nawzad & Said, 2018).

Teachers should be provided with more opportunities to further develop their abilities and receive training, such as by attending to a series of seminars on developing and managing virtual instruction that cover topics like development, operations, delivery, maintenance, repair, administration, and security. Technical personnel may be the first group to receive training; they will help faculty members execute virtual teaching in their individual classrooms. Similar to this, Educational leaders may decide to take on the risk of providing teachers with training on how to convert their printed teaching materials into electronic format and become acquainted with the features and functionalities of e-learning platforms, such as how to assist students and promote learning on specific platforms (Dela Rama et al., 2020).

Furthermore, school administrators should engage in the available instructional support (Monteiro and Leite, 2021). Adapted and specialized teacher training programs should be the emphasis of school administrators who need to respond quickly. This requirement is made more pressing by the ambiguity of the next academic years. In addition to teacher training, there are additional elements that can impact students' development of digital competency. School management, educational regulations, and the role of the publishing and technology sectors all have an impact, even though they are uncontrollable factors (Sánchez-Cruzado et al., 2021).

There should also be the support system and technological environment in schools may also make it more difficult for students to become digitally literate. The level of academic staff preparation at the school affected the growth of teachers' digital codependence to some extent (Almazova et al., 2021). The adaptability of the educational platform was largely dependent on the preparedness of the teachers.

It is evident that teachers are adopting digital teaching and learning tools during the COVID-19 pandemic, ready to put their skills into practice, reaping the rewards of doing so, and spreading excellent practices in the workplace. With the COVID-19 pandemic, learning new digital literacy skills is crucial for most education that is provided via online communities and networks. The long-term incorporation of digital technologies into conventional education will transform the digital literacy of educators. Education and technology should work together to support students in acquiring the critical skills required for full participation as citizens in the digital age.

It was also stated that causality could not be inferred owing to the study's design. Furthermore, more research is needed to determine how the teachers' Digital literacy affects their teaching and to discover the elements that contribute to greater (or decreased) levels of literacy. The majority of research publications on digital literacy are from the West, thus it is hoped that the study has helped close the gap in knowledge among in-service school teachers, especially in the Philippines and Mindanao.

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